

Mastitis in dairy cow: Comprehensive Strategies for diagnosis and treatment

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Introduction:

Mastitis is a major economic concern affecting farm animals and buffaloes in India (Das et al., 2018). Mastitis is one of the most widespread and costly diseases impacting the dairy industry today. The annual financial loss due to mastitis exceeds 2 billion dollars, with nearly two-thirds of these losses resulting from subclinical cases that cause reduced milk production and greater volumes of discarded milk (Dohoo *et al.*, 2011b). Mastitis is a disease with multiple causes, characterized by physical, chemical, and microbial alterations in the mammary gland tissue (Hagnestam *et al.*, 2007, Hussain *et al.*, 2012, Lipkens *et al.*, 2019). Mastitis is an inflammatory condition of the mammary gland tissue, resulting from the host's immune response to various etiological agents, predominantly microorganisms colonizing the gland (Bortolami *et al.*, 2015). Mastitis is primarily induced by bacterial infections and can be categorized into different types based on epidemiological factors, notably infectious and environmental mastitis (Garcia, 2004). Infectious mastitis is attributed to pathogenic microorganisms such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, and *Mycoplasma* species, which are transmitted from infected to healthy cows during milking through contaminated fomites, such as milker's hands, towels, or milking equipment. In contrast, environmental mastitis is induced by microorganisms originating from the cow's external environment rather than the milking parlour. Common sources of these pathogens include bedding material, soil, manure, feces, and stagnant water (McInerney et al., 1992; Garcia, 2004).

Risk factors:

Several risk factors are implicated in the occurrence of bovine mastitis, with significant contributions from pathogen, host, and environmental factors (Klaas and Zadoks, 2018). Milking practices are among the most critical risk factors influencing the onset of mammary gland inflammation. Optimal milking practices do not induce tissue damage or heighten mastitis risk. In contrast, milking irregularities, such as vacuum fluctuations, excessive teat-end vacuum levels, and over-milking, contribute to tissue injury, thereby enhancing mastitis susceptibility and elevating somatic cell count (SCC) (Besier *et al.*, 2019, Cerqueira *et al.*, 2018).

Mastitis in cattle is classified into several types:

- **Peracute Mastitis:** Rapid onset with severe systemic and local signs, often leading to coma and death within 6-24 hours.
- **Acute Mastitis:** Commonly seen immediately after parturition, with systemic and local signs similar to Peracute mastitis, but with a longer course (3-5 days). The udder becomes hard, and milk may change in consistency.
- **Subacute Mastitis:** Less severe, with mild local signs and no systemic symptoms.
- **Subclinical Mastitis:** No visible signs, detected only through laboratory tests.
- **Chronic Mastitis:** Long-lasting, with a hard, nodular udder and few clots in milk.

Clinical symptoms:

The severity and development of an infection depend on several factors, such as the

type of pathogen, the animal's age, immune status, general health, and the stage of lactation (Hurley and Theil, 2011). Bovine mastitis is classified into two forms: clinical and subclinical (Garcia, 2004; Abebe et al., 2016). Clinical mastitis is primarily diagnosed through observable signs, including erythema, increased udder temperature, edema, pain, anorexia, pyrexia, decreased milk production, the presence of clots, discoloration, and alterations in milk consistency, with udder inflammation being the predominant clinical feature (Peters et al., 2015). This condition is frequently associated with infections caused by *Staphylococcus* spp., *Escherichia coli*, and disruption of the normal udder microbiota. Mastitis has drastic effects on milk composition leading to a decline in potassium and lactoferrin. It also results in decreased casein, the major protein in milk. As most of the calcium content in milk is associated with casein, the disruption of casein synthesis contributes to its lowered levels in milk. The milk protein continues to undergo further deterioration during processing and storage. Conversely, subclinical mastitis lacks visible changes in the milk, but is characterized by elevated somatic cell counts, increased bacterial load, diminished milk yield, and deterioration in milk quality (Bian et al., 2014). Diagnosis of subclinical mastitis requires laboratory-based analysis or cow-side diagnostic tests, such as the Coliform mastitis Test, followed by microbiological identification of the etiological agent.

Diagnosis of Mastitis:

The initial step in diagnosing mastitis often involves visual inspection, where the milker plays a crucial and irreplaceable role. While conventional diagnostic methods for mastitis are typically qualitative and possess limited sensitivity and specificity, modern diagnostic approaches offer quantitative assessments with significantly higher specificity and sensitivity (Godden et al., 2017; Hussein et al., 2018; Chakraborty et al., 2019). High-sensitivity and high-specificity diagnostic assays are essential for the precise detection of mastitis. Although mastitis can affect all mammalian species, it holds substantial economic significance in dairy cattle and

buffaloes, primarily due to its adverse impact on both the quantity and quality of milk in high-producing animals. Early detection is critical to minimizing these economic losses. Unlike the clinical form, subclinical mastitis presents no visible signs in the milk or udder, making its identification more challenging. Therefore, familiarity with routine screening tests for early diagnosis is essential for timely intervention and effective disease management (Galdhar and Roy, 2003).

The diagnostic approach to mastitis typically involves a combination of routine laboratory and field-based tests to ensure accurate detection.

Physical Examination of the Udder: Clinical evaluation of the mammary gland remains an essential component of mastitis detection. Visual and tactile assessments focus on changes in the udder's shape, size, Consistency, and Observation of supra-mammary lymph nodes. Palpation of teats and teat orifices helps in identifying signs of inflammation, including heat, swelling, pain, or compromised function.

Examination of the milk:

- a) **Physical examination of the milk:** Normal milk is white, while abnormal colours, a putrid odour, varying consistency, and the presence of flakes or clots can indicate different types of mastitis infections.
- b) **Chemical examination of milk:**
 - 1) **pH Determination test:** The normal pH of milk is 6.4 to 6.8. In mastitis occurring during late lactation and the dry period, the concentrations of lactose and casein in milk decrease, while sodium chloride and sodium bicarbonate are transferred from plasma to the alveoli to preserve isotonicity. This physiological alteration leads to an increase in the milk's pH, often reaching 7.4 or higher, accompanied by elevated chloride concentrations.
 - 2) **Bromothymol blue test:** In the Bromothymol Blue test, normal milk produces a yellow color, while a green to greenish-blue color indicates the presence of mastitis.

- 3) **Bromocresol purple test:** Mix 0.5 ml of a 0.9% bromocresol purple solution with 9.5 ml of milk in a test tube. A pale greyish-purple color suggests normal milk, while a deep purple hue indicates abnormal milk.
 - 4) **Chloride Test:** This test identifies elevated chloride levels in milk affected by mastitis. While normal milk contains approximately 0.08-0.14 gm% chloride, Davis (1999) noted that mastitis causes a drop in lactose and a rise in sodium chloride to preserve the milk's osmotic balance, leading to chloride levels exceeding 0.14% during inflammation (Shoukat et al., 2018).
 - 5) **Modified white side test:** This test is based on the elevated white blood cell count in milk. In mastitis cases, white flakes appear, whereas in healthy milk, the mixture remains a uniformly milky and opaque liquid (Shoukat et al., 2018).
 - 6) **California Mastitis Test (CMT):** The CMT is a simple, low-cost, and rapid cow-side test designed to estimate somatic cell counts (SCC) in milk. Somatic cells are composed of approximately 75 per cent of leucocytes (white blood cells) and 25 per cent of epithelial cells (secretory and lining cells). Changes are visually scored using a five-point scale: negative, trace, weak positive, distinct positive, and strong positive (Adkins & Middleton, 2018; Lam et al., 2009).
 - 7) **Strip cup test:** The strip cup or strip plate test is commonly used in milking Parlors to detect clinical mastitis in individual animals and herds. As part of herd health management, milking machine operators inspect the foremilk by squirting a few streams onto the strip cup. Visible signs such as blood, clots, flakes, or watery consistency indicate possible mastitis.
 - 8) **Somatic cell counts of milk:** Somatic cell count (SCC) is a widely recognized phenotypic marker for detecting mastitis, particularly in its subclinical stage. It reflects the total immune cell population in milk, primarily consisting of neutrophils, lymphocytes, and macrophages (Damm et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2018). Methods used to measure SCC include direct microscopic somatic cell count (DMSCC), bulk milk somatic cell count (BMSCC), and individual cow somatic cell count (ICSCC).
 - 9) **Methylene blue reduction test (MBRT):** The Methylene Blue Reduction Test assesses the chemical activity, particularly the bacterial respiratory activity, in milk. Microorganisms consume oxygen through respiration, and once the oxygen and other reducible components in the milk are depleted, the methylene blue changes from blue to colorless (methylene white) (Davis, 1999).
- c) **Physics-Based Methods**
- 1) **Electrical conductivity test:** The conductivity of milk may be defined as the property of substances in solution which can ionize and therefore can conduct an electrical current. When the concentration of sodium chloride rises in milk, the conductivity rises proportionately. Therefore, measurement of electrical conductivity is used as a simple physical method to diagnose mastitis. EC depends on the concentration of anions and cations in milk. Cows with mastitis have an elevated concentration of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in their milk, which causes an increase in EC (Youssif *et al.*, 2021).
 - 2) **Infrared thermography:** (IRT) imaging can be used to diagnose subclinical mastitis.
 - 3) **Ultrasonography:** It is another helpful non-invasive technique used in the diagnosis of mastitis. It provides additional information about the appearance of the parenchyma and teats and helps to determine a likely prognosis for the animal. However, this technique requires extensive experience (Hallowell and Palgrave, 2012).
 - d) **Acute-Phase Proteins:** Recently, the measurement of acute-phase proteins (APPs) in blood serum or milk has been validated as indicators of mammary

gland inflammation in cows. APPs are synthesized in the liver during an acute inflammatory response (Jain et al., 2011). Key APPs in ruminants include haptoglobin (Hp), serum amyloid A (SAA), fibrinogen, and ceruloplasmin (Viguier et al., 2009; Thomas et al., 2015). A popular diagnostic biomarker for evaluating bovine MAST is haptoglobin (acute phase protein) (Kalmus et al., 2013).

e) Genetic Methods: At present, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) tests are commonly used for the rapid identification of pathogenic microorganisms (Spittel and Hoedemaker, 2012). Advanced techniques such as MALDI-TOF and commercially available quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) tests are vital for the accurate identification of microbes.

f) Microscopic Examination of Milk:

- i. Staining of Milk Smear:** Reveals the presence and type of leukocytes and bacteria under a microscope.
- ii. Counting of Milk Leukocytes:** Helps estimate somatic cell count, indicating inflammation or infection.
- iii. Culturing of Milk:** Identifies specific causative organisms responsible for mastitis through bacterial growth.

Treatment: Effective management of mastitis relies on administering antibiotics along with providing supportive care to the affected animal.

Treatment of Peracute and Acute mastitis:

Antibiotic Therapy: Administer the antibacterial agent both parenterally and intramammarily. **Intramammary infusions:** Two main types of intramammary formulations—commercially available oily ointments and aqueous solutions—are typically used for treating mild to moderate mastitis cases.

- 1. Antibacterial Agents:** Commonly used antibiotics include penicillin, streptomycin, ampicillin, neomycin sulfate, oxytetracycline (Terramycin), cloxacillin, and cefquinome.

- 2. 5% Dextrose as a Carrier:** Studies suggest that delivering antibiotics in 5% dextrose is more effective and less irritating than using distilled water, as dextrose has a soothing effect.

- 3. Intramammary Corticosteroids:** These helps stabilize lysosomes and cell membranes, preventing the release of enzymes and endotoxins, while also reducing inflammation, pain, and managing toxemia.

- 4. Pus Removal:** Administer 10–30 units of oxytocin intravenously or intramuscularly to stimulate milk let-down and facilitate pus drainage from the udder.

- 5. Intramammary Immunoglobulins:** Using 150 mg of immunoglobulins in combination with antibiotics yields better therapeutic outcomes than using either component alone.

Parenteral treatment: For acute or severe mastitis, systemic antibiotic treatment is typically combined with intramammary therapy. Commonly used drugs include oxytetracycline, cephalosporins, amoxicillin, trimethoprim, chloramphenicol, tylosin, ceftiofur, and penicillin-streptomycin. Conducting culture and sensitivity tests helps ensure the correct antibiotic is chosen.

Targeted Treatment for Specific Pathogens:

- i. *Streptococcus agalactiae*:** Responds well to intramammary antibiotic therapy, with a high cure rate.
- ii. *Staphylococcus aureus*:** Treat newly infected animals and consider culling those with chronic infections.

Anti-inflammatory Therapy:

NSAIDs like flunixin meglumine or meloxicam are used to lower fever, reduce pain, and reduce udder inflammation. Antihistamines may also be given to counteract histamine effects.

Supportive Care:

- **Fluid Therapy (IV or oral):** Addresses dehydration and systemic complications.
- **Frequent Milking or Stripping:** Aids in clearing toxins and pathogens from the udder.
- **Electrolytes and Energy Supplements:**

Especially beneficial in animals showing systemic involvement.

Treatment of Subacute and chronic mastitis:

Systemic (parenteral) treatment is generally avoided; instead, local intramammary infusions are administered for 3–5 days. Chronic cases often involve udder fibrosis, for which no effective allopathic treatment exists.

Treatment of Subclinical mastitis:

Usually addressed during the dry period by infusing 200–300 mg of cloxacillin suspended in 3% aluminum monostearate into the udder.

Initial Care Measures:

- Apply cold packs to the udder to reduce swelling.
- Regularly milk out and properly dispose of contaminated milk to prevent further infection.

Prevention and Control:

Routine screening of udder and milk for mastitis, along with prompt isolation and treatment of infected animals, is essential. Maintaining good milking hygiene, including pre- and post-milking teat dipping, is critical. Additional preventive measures include dry cow therapy, ongoing udder health monitoring using tests like somatic cell count or MCMT, and vaccination against pathogens such as *E. coli* or *Staphylococcus aureus* based on herd history. Culling persistently infected or unresponsive animals may be necessary to safeguard the overall health of the herd.

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